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InSAR monitoring of ground deformation related to dewatering of civil works. Case of Glòries square, Barcelona.

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Abstract:	<p>The increasing density of the cities requires new infrastructures and their construction at a greater depth. Therefore, civil works below the water table are more frequent, and so are the associated risks. In this context, a higher control of these activities is needed, and SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) interferometry appears as a technique not only suitable for the monitoring of the ground deformation at local scale, but also as a complement of great value to other common techniques such as levelling, as it provides a more complete view in space and time of the observed phenomena. The aim of this paper is to show how the integration of SAR interferometry and levelling enhances a complete understanding and monitoring of the ground deformation. Their complementarity is illustrated with the construction works of a road tunnel under Glòries square in Barcelona, in which SAR interferometry is part of the continuous monitoring of the works performed by the Construction Management.</p>
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Barcelona, 13 August 2020

Dear editor,

With great pleasure we submit an original manuscript entitled **“InSAR monitoring of ground deformation related to dewatering of civil works. Case of Glòries square, Barcelona.”**, by Joan Botey i Bassols, Enric Vázquez Suñé, Michele Crosetto, Anna Barra and Pierre Gerard, for consideration by Engineering Geology. This is an original work that has not been published elsewhere nor is currently under consideration for publication elsewhere.

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) interferometry has opened new horizons in the monitoring of deformation phenomena of the ground surface. One of its great advantages when working with satellite imagery is the ability to monitor large areas. Consequently, most of the works analysing this technique have been conducted at regional scale. In addition, due to the difficulty of having other data at these scales to compare InSAR results with (such as levelling or GPS data), these studies are often more qualitative than quantitative, focusing on deformation pattern or temporal evolution. Nevertheless, some studies do perform a quantitative analysis at "local" scale, for instance at building scale. In any case, comparisons with other techniques present SAR interferometry in terms of alternative.

Our aim in this paper is to address all three aspects, and especially the last one as it is the main contribution. We present a study of the performance of SAR interferometry when working at local scale, even in such a changing and challenging environment as a construction site; the analysis includes both qualitative and quantitative aspects, spatial pattern of deformation, temporal evolution and magnitude; and we highlight the advantages of an integrated monitoring with SAR interferometry and levelling, emphasizing the complementarity of the strengths of both techniques. All of this taking advantage of the construction works of a road tunnel under Glòries square in Barcelona, in which SAR interferometry is included in the monitoring of the works.

We hope this paper will be of your interest.

We thank you for your time and attention, and look forward to hearing from you.

Best regards,

Joan Botey i Bassols

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InSAR monitoring of ground deformation related to dewatering of civil works. Case of Glòries square, Barcelona.

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Abstract

The increasing density of the cities requires new infrastructures and their construction at a greater depth. Therefore, civil works below the water table are more frequent, and so are the associated risks. In this context, a higher control of these activities is needed, and SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) interferometry appears as a technique not only suitable for the monitoring of the ground deformation at local scale, but also as a complement of great value to other common techniques such as levelling, as it provides a more complete view in space and time of the observed phenomena. The aim of this paper is to show how the integration of SAR interferometry and levelling enhances a complete understanding and monitoring of the ground deformation. Their complementarity is illustrated with the construction works of a road tunnel under Glòries square in Barcelona, in which SAR interferometry is part of the continuous monitoring of the works performed by the Construction Management.

Keywords: SAR interferometry; dewatering; civil works; hydrogeology; levelling.

Highlights

- SAR interferometry as monitoring technique in civil works.
- Ground deformation related to the dewatering of construction works.
- Hydrogeological interpretation of InSAR results.
- Complementarity of SAR interferometry and levelling.

1. Introduction

The work of technicians and researchers who play a role in land management is explicitly or implicitly guided by the concept of risk. Risk is the product of the probability of a certain phenomenon to occur and the damage that this could cause. Thus, the highest socio-economic risks are usually concentrated in urban areas and the highest environmental risks, in the areas of high ecological value. In urban areas, a common problem in risk management

is the interaction between multiple agents acting on the environment. In such cases, detaching the contribution of each agent in the resulting global situation is often a complex task, yet necessary for the responsible management authority (Bansal et al., 2013; Corominas et al., 2014; Flower et al., 2018; Svalova, 2018).

Risks in urban areas are not only high and complex to manage but also more and more frequent. The natural evolution of the city itself makes the space increasingly scarce. In the early stages, when available space is still abundant, infrastructures are built on the surface for simplicity and economy. As the space becomes occupied and the city becomes denser, the infrastructures are buried to free up the progressively more valuable space in surface. At first, they are buried near the surface, again for technical and economic convenience. But the occupation of the underground space also increases, and it becomes necessary to work at greater depths (Eddies et al., 2020; Herce and Magrinyà, 2002; Duranton and Puga, 2014). This leads to the fact that, in consolidated urban environments, infrastructures are often built below the water table, requiring a dewatering –at least– during their construction (Pujades et al., 2014). Therefore, the risks associated with these operations become more and more usual: from small settlements, which may or may not be differential depending on the geological context, to sinkholes and collapses in the worst cases (Clarke and Laefer, 2014; Cheng et al., 2020; Font-Capó et al., 2011; Font-Capó et al., 2015; Haack, 2010; Jurado et al., 2012; Pujades et al., 2012). In other words: the risks related to civil works in urban environments are increasing, and the administrations need to control and manage them (Clarke and Laefer, 2014; Eddies et al., 2020; Vázquez-Suñé et al., 2005).

In this context, regarding soil deformation, the most common and consolidated monitoring techniques, such as levelling, provide high accuracy and reliability but, being point-like techniques, they lack a vision, often in time but especially in space, that makes it difficult to have a complete view of the problem. Here, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) interferometry appears to be a very useful tool, as it is capable of detecting and measuring deformation with a high sampling density both in space and time, without having to face the dilemma of prioritizing the spatial density over the extension of the monitored area or vice versa (Karila et al., 2013; Serrano-Juan et al., 2017).

SAR Interferometry (InSAR) is a family of radar techniques that allow for the measurement of deformation of the ground surface. It is economically competitive and able to measure sub-centimetric deformations with a high spatial density, without being affected by meteorology or daylight and with an automatic data acquisition. In addition, when using satellite data, it covers large areas (100–10 000's of km²), a new SAR image is available every few days (6 for Sentinel-1) and a historic archive is available, allowing for retrospective studies (Carnec and Delacourt, 2000; Galloway and Hoffmann, 2007). Ground-Based radar (GB-SAR) also exists. It covers smaller areas (few km² at most) but is able to observe the study scene every few minutes (Minati et al., 2014; Montserrat et al., 2014).

InSAR working principle consists in measuring the difference on the wave phase between two radar images, acquired at different times over the same scene. The phase is related to the distance between the radar and the ground and, more specifically, the change in the phase between two instants is directly related to the deformation of the ground surface. The complexity of SAR data processing is that deformation is not the only factor that may

alter the wave phase. The processing consists in isolating the deformation from the other contributions, like the topographic, the atmospheric and the thermal expansion components, and noise (Crosetto et al., 2016).

The bibliography already offers studies in which the performance of SAR interferometry is analysed, notably regarding the spatial pattern of the deformation and its temporal evolution. See for instance Cabral-Cano, 2008; Del Soldato, 2018; Galloway and Burbey, 2011; Galloway and Hoffmann, 2007; Lu and Danskin, 2001; Tomás et al., 2005. Quantitative analyses regarding the accuracy and precision of InSAR results are scarcer, even though some papers have already addressed this issue too. Indeed, comparisons with other point-like techniques such as levelling or GPS can be found, among others, in Jiang and Lin, 2010; Mahmoudpour et al., 2016; Motagh et al., 2017; Perski et al., 2009; Yerro et al., 2014. However, most of these cases are at regional scale, and there are fewer cases of quantitative comparison between SAR interferometry and levelling at local scale (i.e., for instance, at construction site scale), where a higher quality of the data is necessary not only at dataset but specially at point level since less data is available for a grouped analysis. Nevertheless, Karila et al., 2013 conduct a comparison of the subsidence rates of building foundations obtained with both techniques; and in Serrano-Juan et al., 2017, InSAR and levelling results are compared in a case study of ground settlements associated to the dewatering of construction civil works also in an urban area. Both cases show the potential of SAR interferometry in urban areas at building scale, although its precision often remains an open issue.

All the mentioned works have analysed and compared the performance of SAR interferometry with other techniques. The aim of this paper is to highlight how the integrated use of levelling and SAR interferometry in the monitoring of ground deformation allows to take advantage of their complementary strengths: the high accuracy and reliability of levelling; and the broader and denser view of SAR interferometry. The results of this integration in the case of the construction works of a road tunnel under Glòries square in Barcelona and the subsequent dewatering of the excavation, highlight the difficulty of understanding the whole deformation phenomenon with point-like monitoring techniques. SAR interferometry proves to be crucial in identifying the origin of the deformation and its controlling factors. Moreover, in this case SAR interferometry is included in the continuous monitoring of the works performed by the Construction Management office, thus proving the suitability of this technique to monitor deformation phenomena, not only at local scale but in addition in such challenging and changing contexts as construction sites.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Geographical, geological and hydrogeological setting

Glòries square is one of the main connections of the city of Barcelona with the north and northeast, both for railway and road traffic (Fig. 1). A road tunnel is under construction to bypass the square and free the surface from traffic. The area is complex since it gathers several first order infrastructures, many of them quite ancient and, thus, weakened by time: 3 train tunnels, 1 metro tunnel; 1 main sewer and 1 main service gallery. The presence of these

underground infrastructures has made it necessary for the new tunnel to pass underneath, at greater depth. As a result, a significant dewatering is needed, which might produce settlements of the terrain. In addition, in the last 15-20 years some major accidents in public works have occurred in Barcelona, which have caused concern from both citizens and authorities. This situation has motivated a rigorous control of the construction works.

Fig. 1.- Location of Glòries square in Barcelona and primary transport network of the city: yellow, road network; orange, railway network. White dashed line shows the location of Fig. 2. (Background image: Google Earth)

Barcelona is mainly located in the Barcelona Plain, limited by the Collserola range to the northwest (top in Fig. 1), the Mediterranean Sea to the southeast (bottom), Besòs river to the northeast (right) and Llobregat river to the southwest (left). The geology of the area can be divided into three levels: from surface to depth, anthropic fill, Quaternary units and Pliocene units. The anthropic fill is very heterogeneous in composition and thickness, but not thicker than 6 metres. The Quaternary strata (Fig. 2) present an important lithological limit oriented north-to-south that corresponds to the limit of the Besòs river delta. At the east side of this limit, the delta deposits consist mainly of three layers: well-sorted sands at the top and gravels at the bottom with silts and clays in between. On the west side, two units can be distinguished in the Barcelona Plain: dominant colluvial deposits coming from the erosion of the granites of the Collserola range, and alluvial deposits associated with the drainage network. The colluvial deposits are very heterometric, from conglomerates to sandstones in a very abundant clayey matrix, and have a certain degree of cementation. The alluvial deposits constitute the filling of ancient streams and are composed mainly of gravels in a clayey matrix. Finally, there are the Pliocene underlying units (Fig. 2), which constitute the pre-Quaternary substrate. These units are located at a depth from 10 m inland (Glòries square) to 55 m near the

sea. Their topography changes from steeper and rougher near the Collserola range, where ancient streams eroded these units, to flatter and smoother in the Besòs delta area, closer to the sea. Two Pliocene units can also be identified. The upper unit consists of sands and gravels with a sandy clay matrix, while the lower unit consists of clays and blue marls, both units of marine origin. Two main fault families, oriented northwest-southeast and southwest-northeast, divide and compartmentalize these formations, with the northwest-southeast faults being the most important ones. For a more detailed geological description, see Vázquez-Suñé et al., 2016.

Fig. 2.- Geological context, with (top) and without (bottom) Quaternary units. See location in Fig. 1. Hydrogeological cross-section A-A' is shown in Fig. 3. (Modified from Vázquez-Suñé et al. 2016)

Focusing on Glòries, the square is located just above two important (hydro)geological features: the boundary between the Besòs delta and the colluvial Quaternary units; and a major northwest-southeast fault in the underlying Pliocene strata, which also represents a change in the lithology, from marls in the southwest to sandstones in the northeast. From the hydrogeological point of view, the Besòs delta can be described as three aquifers separated by two aquitards, whose thickness increases toward the sea (Velasco et al., 2012). Given that Glòries is situated at the edge of the delta, the square is located where the aquitards virtually disappear and all three aquifers connect (Fig. 3), in a zone where the whole Quaternary materials have a limited thickness. There are five recharge sources in this area: infiltrated rainfall in Collserola, leaks from the water supply and sewer networks, recharge from the Besòs river (to a great extent, treated wastewater), urban runoff and marine intrusion (Vàzquez-Suñé et al., 2010). In undisturbed conditions, the main groundwater flux goes from the Collserola range to the Mediterranean Sea (northwest to southeast), except for the surroundings of the Besòs river, where the interaction with the river dominates the local piezometry.

Fig. 3.- Schematic hydrogeological cross-section of the Quaternary materials. In reality, in the area of Glòries square, Quaternary materials have a reduced thickness, and the lower aquitard does not isolate anymore the lower and the main aquifers. Approximate scale: 4 km x 100 m. See location in Fig. 2. (Modified from Velasco et al. 2012).

2.2 Civil works description

The works consist of the construction of a tunnel by the cut-and-cover method, except for three sections passing under crossing pre-existing tunnels (orange area and circles in Fig. 4). During the study period (until autumn 2018),

the works were mainly limited to Glòries square itself (green area in the figure), although the total extension of the works will be greater (adding the red area in the figure). Thus, the excavation during the study was 500 m long, 25 m wide and up to 30 m deep (under the pre-existing tunnels), getting the deepest retaining walls up to 50 m deep. This implies that, although in most of the area affected by the dewatering of the excavation only Quaternary materials are drained, in the works area itself also the underlying Pliocene materials are drained.

The retaining walls have some shallower sections, drawing a comb in the profile, which aims to minimize the obstruction of the aquifer section (observe that the axis of the tunnel is perpendicular to the main groundwater flux). The walls are convenient not only from the construction point of view –making it easier, cheaper and safer– but also from the hydrological point of view. To a certain degree, an enclosure isolates the excavation from the surroundings, in such a way that the volume to be drained is reduced –minimizing the economic cost– and the drawdown outside the enclosure is smaller –reducing the deformation of the terrain. In Glòries square, the retaining walls are slurry walls.

Prior to the works, in August 2015 the water table was at 14 m depth in Glòries square, what implies the need for a 16 m lowering at the lowest point. The dewatering of the excavation began on the 23rd January 2017. Until the works were temporarily stopped in May 2017, 1 hm³ was drained by means of up to 36 wells during the transient stage (yellow and red points in Fig. 4). Some of these wells are located within the enclosure and some outside (in the junctions with the pre-existing crossing tunnels), being all of them screened all along (except for the deepest meter). During this first dewatering stage, the total discharge rate ranged from 30 to 420 L/s (Fig. 9). The works resumed in March 2018 and were expected to proceed for 32 months. This paper is focused on this second dewatering stage, in which the stabilized pumping rate was approximately 155 L/s distributed in 13 wells (red points in Fig. 4). Note the greatest density of pumping wells in the northeast part of the excavation (right-hand side in the figure), reflecting the change in transmissivity between colluvial and deltaic materials, being much greater in the latter.

Fig. 4.- Geometry of the construction works and drainage network. Top: cross-section; bottom: plan view. Green: area under construction during the study; red: area not yet under construction during the study. See location in Fig. 5. (Modified from BIMSA, Ajuntament de Barcelona).

2.3 Data

In order to monitor eventual ground movements during the construction works, Glòries square area is being monitored with SAR interferometry since May 2015 (Fig. 5). The processed dataset is composed of 97 descending IWS (Interferometric Wide Swath) SLC (Single Look Complex) Sentinel-1A images from 06/03/2015 to 28/09/2018 (Table 1). Five other images were discarded due to strong atmospheric effects (grey in the table). For most of the images, the time separation was 12 days, even though in some cases it was either 6 or 24 days.

Fig. 5.- Area studied with SAR interferometry (green line) within Barcelona. Red ellipse: Glòries square. Red rectangle: excavation. Blue rectangle: extent of Fig. 4 and Fig. 10. (Embedded satellite image: ESRI; background main image: Ajuntament de Barcelona).

The applied SAR data treatment is a Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) technique described in detail in Crosetto et al. 2018 and Devanthery et al. 2014. The main steps are:

- (1) Precise co-registration of the images based on the information provided by the orbits.
- (2) Generation of two redundant networks of interferograms: full-resolution or single-look (pixel footprint: 4 by 14 m) and 10 in range by 2 in azimuth (10 x 2) multi-look (pixel footprint: 40 by 28 m).
- (3) Candidate Persistent Scatterer (PS) selection based on the SAR amplitude dispersion.
- (4) 2 + 1D (space + time) phase unwrapping of the redundant 10 x 2 multi-look interferograms.
- (5) Identification of stable areas in the surroundings of the area of interest. In this case, according to the piezometry maps (Fig. 7), it has been assumed that no deformation takes place further than 1 km from Glòries square.
- (6) Estimation of the atmospheric phase component over stable areas, in this case assuming a spatial linear phase model.
- (7) Prediction and removal of the estimated atmospheric component from the original single-look interferograms.
- (8) Using the atmospheric-free single-look interferograms, estimation of linear deformation velocity and Residual Topographic Error (RTE).
- (9) Removal of the RTE from the atmospheric-free single-look interferograms.

- (10) 2 + 1D phase unwrapping of RTE- and atmospheric-free single-look interferograms.
- (11) Generation of the deformation time series and estimation of the deformation velocity.
- (12) Geocoding of the results.

Image	Orbit	Date									
1	6132	29/05/2015	26	11207	11/05/2016	51	15932	31/03/2017	76	20482	06/02/2018
2	6307	10/06/2015	27	11382	23/05/2016	52	16107	12/04/2017	77	20657	18/02/2018
3	6657	04/07/2015	28	11557	04/06/2016	53	16282	24/04/2017	78	20832	02/03/2018
4	6832	16/07/2015	29	11907	28/06/2016	54	16457	06/05/2017	79	21007	14/03/2018
5	7007	28/07/2015	30	12082	10/07/2016	55	16632	18/05/2017	80	21182	26/03/2018
	7182	09/08/2015	31	12257	22/07/2016		16807	30/05/2017	81	21357	07/04/2018
6	7357	21/08/2015	32	12432	03/08/2016	56	16982	11/06/2017	82	21532	19/04/2018
7	7707	14/09/2015	33	12607	15/08/2016	57	17157	23/06/2017	83	21707	01/05/2018
8	7882	26/09/2015	34	12782	27/08/2016	58	17332	05/07/2017	84	21882	13/05/2018
9	8057	08/10/2015	35	12957	08/09/2016	59	17507	17/07/2017	85	22057	25/05/2018
10	8407	01/11/2015	36	13132	20/09/2016	60	17682	29/07/2017		22232	06/06/2018
11	8582	13/11/2015		13307	02/10/2016	61	17857	10/08/2017	86	22407	18/06/2018
12	8757	25/11/2015	37	13482	14/10/2016	62	18032	22/08/2017	87	22582	30/06/2018
13	8932	07/12/2015	38	13657	26/10/2016	63	18207	03/09/2017	88	22757	12/07/2018
14	9107	19/12/2015	39	13832	07/11/2016	64	18382	15/09/2017	89	22932	24/07/2018
15	9282	31/12/2015	40	14007	19/11/2016	65	18557	27/09/2017	90	23107	05/08/2018
16	9457	12/01/2016	41	14182	01/12/2016	66	18732	09/10/2017	91	12211	11/08/2018
17	9632	24/01/2016	42	14357	13/12/2016	67	18907	21/10/2017	92	23282	17/08/2018
18	9807	05/02/2016	43	14532	25/12/2016	68	19082	02/11/2017	93	12386	23/08/2018
19	9982	17/02/2016	44	14707	06/01/2017	69	19257	14/11/2017		12561	04/09/2018
20	10157	29/02/2016	45	14882	18/01/2017	70	19432	26/11/2017	94	23632	10/09/2018
21	10332	12/03/2016	46	15057	30/01/2017	71	19607	08/12/2017	95	12736	16/09/2018
22	10507	24/03/2016	47	15232	11/02/2017	72	19782	20/12/2017	96	23807	22/09/2018
23	10682	05/04/2016	48	15407	23/02/2017	73	19957	01/01/2018	97	12911	28/09/2018
24	10857	17/04/2016	49	15582	07/03/2017	74	20132	13/01/2018			
25	11032	29/04/2016	50	15757	19/03/2017	75	20307	25/01/2018			

Table 1.- List of the IWS SLC Sentinel-1A SAR images used in this study. The grey ones have been discarded because of strong atmospheric effects.

A final smoothing has then been applied to the resulting time series aiming to remove the noise that made the interpretation of the results not straightforward, especially regarding the spatial distribution. The term noise here refers to any contribution not strictly related to the deformation process. This can include residual atmospheric effects, residual orbital errors, residual topographic errors, phase unwrapping errors, phase noise, etc. Some of these sources show a correlation with time and/or space, some none. Therefore, since the smoothing is applied to the time series in an individual and independent way (i.e. without involving any consideration in terms of space), it reduces only the noise that is temporally uncorrelated (i.e. independent from time). However, most of this

temporally uncorrelated noise appears to be spatially correlated in the case of Glòries, which has turned into a clear improvement in the maps.

The smoothing has consisted of two steps: first, a moving median over 5 dates of data acquisition; second, a moving average over 3 dates. The width of the moving median and the fitting of the smoothing have been calibrated and verified using 14 control time series, grouped in 7 pairs distributed all around the study area. Each pair contained two close points, one point with large noise and another one with small noise. The selection of the control time series and the grouping in pairs aim to obtain a control data subset representative of the whole dataset, and is based on the map of noise. The first step removes most of the noise, but the time series become rough. Then, in the second step, the moving average is applied over 3 dates in order to smooth but alter the least the time series.

In the analysis of the results, other data have been used: geology, hydraulic parameters of the terrain, piezometric data and levelling surveying. IDAEA-CSIC had already carried on a local revision of the geology in previous works, and a hydrogeological numerical model had been built up (Velasco et al. 2012; Vázquez-Suñé et al. 2016). From this information, new boreholes drilled for the works in Glòries square and pumping tests on some of the drainage wells of the works, a refined local hydrogeological model has been built up. Hydraulic parameters of the terrain such as transmissivity and storage coefficient have been extracted from this model. The values obtained are consistent with the hydraulic parametrisation of other tunnelling works in the vicinity (Pujades et al., 2014b, 2015, 2016).

The Construction Management office (CM) has provided the geometry of the works and the structures, included in the numerical model and taken into account in the interpretation of the field measurements. CM has also provided the location of drainage wells and monitoring piezometers, and the time series of pumping discharge rates and groundwater heads. These data are complemented with periodic field campaigns performed by IDAEA-CSIC in the surroundings of the works, before and during the works, which provides a wider spatial and temporal context. These campaigns provide, among other parameters, the groundwater head, i.e. the piezometry and its evolution.

Finally, CM has also provided the location of the points of the levelling monitoring network and their time series of deformation. These data have allowed a comparison with InSAR results. The dataset consists of a network of 170 monitored levelling bolts fixed to building façades along the axis of the tunnel (Fig. 10), and a network of 36 reference bases fixed to the ground located within an approximate distance of 450 m all around Glòries square.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Hydrogeological discussion

One of the results of SAR interferometry are maps of accumulated displacements of the ground surface, in the form of a cloud of georeferenced points or pixels. In the case here discussed, InSAR results show a settlement area right

eastward from Glòries square (Fig. 6), with maximum settlements of around -7 mm. The rest of the observed scene is approximately stable.

Fig. 6.- Vertical displacements of the ground surface accumulated during the second dewatering stage of the works in Glòries square (~03/04/2018 – 23/08/2018). The red rectangle shows the extent of the excavation. See Fig. 5 for a clearer location. The median of the InSAR time series within the black circle is shown in Fig. 9, as well as the water head time series of the black point. (Background image: Ajuntament de Barcelona).

Analysing the spatial distribution of the deformation, given that, a priori, in the presented case study the deformation is expected to be related to the drawdown caused by dewatering of civil works, one of the most surprising aspects of the InSAR results might be that the settlements are not centred and distributed around the construction area but concentrated in the east quadrant (Fig. 6). In any case, this fact is in good agreement with the local geology and the observed drawdown.

Regarding the geology, three aspects are relevant. First, eastward from Glòries square, Quaternary materials correspond to the Besòs river delta (Fig. 2), which is formed by three aquifers separated by two aquitards (Fig. 3). At district scale, the drawdown occurs mainly in the Quaternary materials, despite that at the scale of the

construction site Pliocene materials are also drained. In particular, in the delta, the dewatering of the construction works in Glòries square drains the shallow deltaic aquifer, which also affects the upper aquitard. As a fine-grained unit, the aquitard is more deformable than the surrounding colluvial materials of the Barcelona Plain, i.e. westward from Glòries square. Second, these colluvial materials contain several cemented levels, what makes them stiffer. Together, both aspects predict larger settlements eastward from Glòries square, even for a uniform drawdown. And third, the shallow deltaic aquifer is more transmissive than the colluvial and alluvial materials of the Barcelona Plain, which entails a greater spread of the drawdown, i.e. a more extensive cone eastward from the excavation.

Regarding the piezometry, the spatial distribution of the deformation is in strong agreement with the drawdown measured in the field (Fig. 7). The phreatic surface has been built up with the water head manually measured in two sets of piezometers: on the one side, the control network of the construction works; and on the other side, the control network of the City Council of Barcelona in the district. In the latter case, the piezometers are shallow and measure the water head of the shallow aquifer. In the former case, the piezometers are deeper (up to 30 m deep) and measure the head of the converged lower, main and shallow aquifers. The drawdown distribution is possibly due to three reasons: the natural groundwater flux goes from northwest to southeast (i.e. toward the Mediterranean sea); the lithology is more transmissive eastward; and several other dewatering operations follow one another since the 2000's southeast and eastward from Glòries square, even though the dewatering in Glòries is much greater. These successive third-party dewaterings may explain why the largest deformation is detected not in the construction area itself (centre of the current piezometric cone) but toward southeast, notably if taking into account that the largest settlements are located where a piezometric depression cone was already detected before the construction works in Glòries square began (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7.- Phreatic surface of the study area in November 2018. Levels are expressed in meters above sea level (m.a.s.l.). The time series of the red dot (black dot in Fig. 6) is shown in Fig. 9. The black circle is the same of Fig. 6 and Fig. 8. (Background image: Ajuntament de Barcelona).

Fig. 8.- Phreatic surface of the study area in 2016 (levels in m.a.s.l.). Observe the local piezometric cone south-east from Glòries square, pointed and coloured in red. The black circle is the same of Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. Red points are third-party dewatering operations carried on in the last years. (Modified from previous works by IDAEA-CSIC).

SAR interferometry can also provide the time series of accumulated displacement of each point or pixel. These results show that the evolution of the deformation in the area of Glòries square follows the one of the water table, which in turn is opposed to that of the drainage discharge rate (Fig. 9). This confirms that the drawdown related to the works in Glòries square dominates the dynamics of the area, despite the existence of several other dewatering operations nearby. In summary, geology and piezometry get combined and perfectly explain the observations made by SAR interferometry, both in space and time.

Fig. 9.- Green: time evolution of accumulated vertical displacement of the ground surface with respect to 29/05/2015 in the centre of the settling area (black circle in Fig. 6 to Fig. 8), measured with SAR interferometry. Blue: time evolution of the piezometric level in the works area (black dot in Fig. 6, red in Fig. 7). Grey: time evolution of the total pumping rate of the dewatering in the works of Glòries square.

The temporal evolution also justifies why this paper can easily focus only on the second dewatering stage of the construction works in Glòries square, i.e. since the works resumed in March 2018 after a stop of some months: the settlements produced during the first stage fully recovered before the second stage began (Fig. 9), in such a way that the deformations described in this paper are related only to the second stage (at least, for that regarding the works in Glòries square). This also means that the deformation undergone during the first stage of dewatering showed to be reversible, which will be recalled later in the last part of the discussion. The largest settlements since the second stage began (~03/04/2018) were of -7 mm by the end of August 2018, very similar to the value observed during the first stage, of -7.5 mm.

3.2 Comparison with levelling data

Available levelling data from the monitoring of the works allow for a comparison with InSAR results. Since these data are concentrated along the axis of the tunnel (Fig. 10), the comparison is based on two profiles along the tunnel, one on the northwest (“mountain”) side and one on the southeast (“sea”) side, for both interferometry and levelling (Fig. 11). In other words, and to make it clearer for the reader: from now on, the analysis zooms in from the district scale to the excavation scale.

When analysing the results, and especially when comparing both techniques, it must be kept in mind that they both measure specific points that might not strictly follow the trend of the area, depending on their physical support and its mechanical bond with the surroundings. For instance, there can be a point located on the sidewalk of a street and another one located on the roof of an adjacent building. Given that the former is located directly on the terrain whereas the latter is on a structure with foundations, their deformation can be different. The same situation arises if two close points are located on two different buildings that are founded on different strata. This is especially relevant in the case of SAR interferometry because there is no prior control on the location of the measuring points (pixels or PS’s, in this case) and because each pixel of a SAR image usually contains several scatterers or reflectors –more or less depending on the observed scene and the spatial resolution of the image. For this reason, the profiles are built with the measurements located in a roughly 25 m wide band along the tunnel and then synthesised (Fig. 11). The results of each technique differ in two aspects: the spatial pattern and the magnitude of the ground movements.

Regarding the spatial pattern, InSAR profiles show larger settlements on the southeast side: -7 mm for the largest settlements, against -3 mm on the northwest side (Fig. 11). However, such a fact is not observed in the levelling profiles, in which the largest settlements are of -1 to -2 mm on both sides. Again, the pattern described by SAR interferometry, in this case larger deformation on the southeast side, makes sense with the local hydrogeology, but now not only regarding the Quaternary materials but also the Pliocene strata. As previously said, at the construction site, the drawdown not only occurs at the former but also at the latter, and this is relevant since, northeast from Glòries square, the axis of the tunnel is aligned with a fault marking a lithological change in the Pliocene materials (Fig. 2): sands on the northwest side and marls on the southeast side, i.e. more deformable materials on the southeast side. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the largest settlements of the profiles occur in Glòries square, as shown by InSAR results, exactly where levelling does not have any measuring point (Fig. 11). In other words: InSAR data allows to describe the ground deformation in the construction area, whereas levelling does not. It is also worth to remind that these profiles do not cross the centre of the settling zone (Fig. 6), so they do not show the absolute largest deformation of the monitored area.

Fig. 10.- Points included in the profiles of Fig. 11: green, InSAR; red, levelling. The red rectangle shows the extent of the excavation. See location of this map in Fig. 5.

Fig. 11.- Profiles of vertical displacements along the tunnel accumulated during the dewatering (2nd stage, between 07/04/2018 and 05/08/2018). Top, B-B', northwest side; bottom, C-C', southeast side (see Fig. 10). Green, SAR interferometry; red, levelling. Coloured lines are interpolations based on the median. The profiles in grey are analytical estimations (Fig. 12) along a profile centred in the tunnel, in between B-B' and C-C', included for comparison.

Regarding the magnitude of the ground movements, the settlements are rather small and, therefore, it is difficult to judge the discrepancy between InSAR and levelling data. Nevertheless, the settlement has been estimated analytically to obtain a third value to compare their results with. The settlement at the top of a ground layer (Δz [L]) related to a given drawdown can be estimated with the equation proposed by Cashman and Preene, 2001:

$$\Delta z = \gamma_w \cdot b \cdot \alpha \cdot \Delta h \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where γ_w is the specific weight of water [L^2MT^{-2}], b is the thickness of the layer [L], α is the compressibility coefficient of the ground [$LM^{-1}T^2$] and Δh is the drawdown [L]. The compressibility coefficient can be associated to the storage coefficient (S []) according to the formula proposed by Jacob, 1950 and cited by Ferris et al., 1962:

$$S = \rho_w \cdot g \cdot b \cdot (\alpha + \theta \cdot \beta_w) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where ρ_w is the density of water [$L^{-3}M$], g is the gravitational acceleration [LT^{-2}], θ is the porosity of the medium [] and β_w is the compressibility coefficient of water [$LM^{-1}T^2$]. Considering that the compressibility of water is usually much smaller than that of the ground, the former is commonly neglected, leading to the following simplification:

$$S \approx \rho_w \cdot g \cdot b \cdot \alpha = \gamma_w \cdot b \cdot \alpha \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Finally, the settlement at the ground surface is estimated as the addition of the settlements occurred at each layer:

$$\Delta z = \sum_i (S_i \cdot \Delta h_i) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where the index i refers to the i -th hydrogeological layer.

The proposed procedure needs some clarifications. First, regarding Eq. 4, in a general case the storage coefficient (S) is not constant and, therefore, the equation is not a linear law. As the aquifer is compacted due to the drawdown and the subsequent increase of the effective stress, it becomes stiffer and the storage coefficient diminishes, in such a way that the relationship between stress (drawdown) and deformation (settlement) follows a logarithmic law (Dassargues, 1995). However, in the case of Glòries square, a constant value for the storage coefficient is here used. It has been obtained through inverse calibration using the local hydrogeological numerical model specifically developed for the design of the dewatering of the construction works. The data used for the calibration come from pumping tests performed in the wells of the works. These tests registered both the drawdown until stabilisation of the groundwater level and its recovery, and were performed with a discharge rate similar to that expected for the dewatering. Thus, the storage coefficient obtained from the interpretation of these tests is unaltered, valid for the applied stresses and representative of the whole area affected by the pumping. Therefore, the obtained value for the storage coefficient can be assumed as an average value valid to be used as a constant in Eq. 4.

The second clarification regards the Eq. 1. This formula assumes that the deformation is purely vertical. This simplifying hypothesis is rather common yet not always true. In a general case of an aquifer where the boundaries do not constrain the deformation of the soil, this deformation will occur both in the vertical and horizontal directions (Pujades et al., 2017). Since the storage coefficient obtained from pumping tests is representative of the real boundary conditions, it will be valid for Eq. 1 only in case that the horizontal deformation is constrained, so the deformation is indeed purely vertical. Otherwise, a correction should be introduced in order to take into account only the contribution of the vertical deformation to the compressibility coefficient (Pujades et al., 2014a):

$$\alpha' = \alpha \cdot \frac{1 + \nu}{3 \cdot (1 - \nu)} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

which, according to Eq. 3, can be expressed in terms of the storage coefficient as follows:

$$S' = S \cdot \frac{1 + \nu}{3 \cdot (1 - \nu)} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where ν is the Poisson's ratio. Observe that the correction reduces the storage coefficient and, therefore, the estimated settlement.

In the case of Glòries, since there are some changes in the deformability and transmissivity of the terrain around the construction site, it is reasonable to think that it is a mixed case, in which the horizontal deformation might be partially constrained: the Quaternary materials are stiffer on the west side of Glòries square, and the Pliocene materials are stiffer on the northwest side of tunnel. Therefore, the analytical estimation of the settlements has been done with and without the correction, thus giving a range of expectable values.

Nevertheless, some other factors may still lead to an overestimation of the settlement:

- In the interpretation of the pumping tests, the water flow is considered to be purely radial. This hypothesis neglects the eventual recharge vertical flows from the unsaturated zone, the saturated but not-pumped zone or from over- or underlying aquitards. If such recharge flows exist, the storage coefficient will be overestimated. In the case of Glòries, the wells are screened all along, so the whole column of the ground is drained, from the surface to the bottom; and the piezometric data do not show any upward recharge flow.
- Eq. 1 estimates the final settlement once the steady state is reached, as seems to be the case in Glòries, according to the time series of water head and deformation. This point is particularly relevant for fine-grained units, which usually concentrate most of the total deformation but take longer to reach a new equilibrium.
- In excavations, the unloading of the terrain due to the removed material causes an uplift of the ground, which compensates (part of) the settlement due to the drawdown. This might be valid for the profiles along the tunnel, but not for the whole observed area.

One last consideration regarding Eq. 1 is worth to mention: this formula is valid for over-consolidated aquifers that behave elastically, that is, valid as long as the effective stress (or, equivalently, the drawdown) does not exceed the maximum ever experienced by the aquifer. This is the case of Barcelona. Like many other cities with an industrial history, the development of the industry in the mid-19th century came with an increasing demand for water. The lack of sufficient supply and the availability of fresh water in good quality and quantity in the highly transmissive deltaic aquifers of Llobregat and Besòs rivers, led to an intensive exploitation of these aquifers. The global abstraction reached a maximum of 60-70 Mm³ per year by the early 1970's, what entailed generalised drawdowns of up to 15 m, approximately (the largest drawdown induced in the current construction works in Glòries square is of 20 m, (Fig. 12). Years later, the contamination of the aquifers and the urbanistic pressure of a growing city motivated a progressive relocation of the industry out of Barcelona, and the piezometric levels started to recover. By the early 2000's, the aquifers had already reached levels similar to those prior to the industrialisation (Vàzquez-Suñé et al. 1997 and 2005). Indeed, the reversibility of the deformation has been observed in this case (Fig. 9), as well as in Pujades et al., 2014a, where the ground deformation on three sites close to Glòries square is analysed.

With all these considerations in mind, the proposed procedure has been applied to the case of Glòries square. With the numerical model and field tests, the storage coefficient has been estimated around $3.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for the colluvial Quaternary materials, $3.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for the deltaic Quaternary materials, $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for the Pliocene marls and $4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for the Pliocene sands. The anthropic filling does not intervene since the water table has always remained underneath

(Fig. 12). An average value of 0.35 has been used for the Poisson's ratio, obtained from Pujades et al., 2014a. And the drawdowns come from field measurements. With these data, the estimated settlements range from -0.5 to -6 mm without the correction, and from -0.4 to -4.2 mm with the correction (Fig. 12).

The analytical results, with and without a correction taking into account eventual constraints on the horizontal deformation, are in between those of InSAR and levelling (Fig. 11). Therefore, and taking into account the small magnitude of the settlements and the lack of levelling data in the excavation area –which is not only a disadvantage with respect to InSAR but also an important limitation to this comparison–, the results of both InSAR and levelling can be considered realistic and possible. However, with all due caution, two considerations can still be added, which would support levelling results: first, the analytical estimation is more likely to overestimate than to underestimate the settlements (because of the previously exposed reasons); and second, levelling measures values similar to those detected in comparable cases nearby (Pujades et al. 2014a, for instance).

Fig. 12.- In brown (also in grey in Fig. 11), settlements of the ground surface estimated analytically along the axis of the tunnel (in between profiles B-B' and C-C' in Fig. 10), with and without a correction taking into account eventual constraints on the horizontal deformation (estimating smaller and larger settlements, respectively). In the background, geological profile. In blue, initial (light) and "final" (dark) piezometric profiles (beginning of the 2nd dewatering stage (13/03/2018) and end of this study (06/08/2018), respectively).

4. Conclusions

This paper has shown the added value of combining usual point-like techniques such as levelling, and SAR interferometry in the monitoring of ground deformation, taking advantage of their complementary strengths: the high accuracy and reliability of levelling; and the broader and denser view of SAR interferometry. This integration has been illustrated with the case of the construction of a road tunnel under Glòries square in Barcelona, in which

SAR interferometry has been included in the monitoring plan of the construction works. These works require a significant dewatering which, consequently, entail ground deformation. Being a site located within a dense urban area, the works require a high control.

SAR interferometry has allowed to observe that the ground deformation is not centred around the construction site –as it could be expected– but concentrated in the east quadrant. This distribution agrees with both piezometry and hydrogeology. The area covered by the levelling network and its density would not have allowed such observation.

In a similar way, levelling would not have made it possible either to observe that, in addition, the largest settlements are not located in the works area but slightly to the southeast. The reason is that, although the temporal evolution of the deformation matches very much the evolution of the dewatering and, therefore, confirms that the works dominate the dynamics of the deformation, several other groundwater pumpings have been and are still active south and eastward from Glòries square.

At a more local scale, i.e. at construction site scale, where the levelling network is denser, the spatial distribution of deformation measured by interferometry is again more consistent with local hydrogeology than levelling.

From the quantitative point of view, SAR interferometry measures larger settlements than levelling, although in both cases the displacements are rather small (sub-centimetric where data from both techniques exist). Analytical estimations are in between. Being this the case and taking into account the magnitude of the measured settlements and the lack of levelling data in the excavation area, the results of both InSAR and levelling can be considered realistic and possible.

In summary, SAR interferometry has shown to be not only a technique suitable for the monitoring of deformation associated with civil works in urban environments, but also a highly valuable complement to usual techniques such as levelling, as it is able to provide a much more complete view of the observed deformation phenomena.

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Contributions

Joan Botey i Bassols: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. Enric Vázquez-Suñé: Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding Acquisition. Michele Crosetto: Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding Acquisition. Anna Barra: Resources. Pierre Gerard: Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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